

ENHANCING INCLUSIVE TEACHING THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: INSIGHTS FROM AN ERASMUS+ PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT COURSE

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Abstract

The digital transformation of education and the rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) offer new opportunities to promote inclusive education and to adapt the teaching process to the diverse needs of students. This paper presents the professional experience gained during the training course "Inclusive Teaching with Artificial Intelligence", held in Athens, Greece, between 18–24 May 2026, within the Erasmus+ project 2025-1-RO01-KA121-SCH-000327310. The activities carried out focused on the use of artificial intelligence-based tools for personalization of information, the development of inclusive educational strategies, the analysis of the ethical issues associated with the use of AI and the use of AI. strengthening teachers' digital skills. The results highlight the potential of artificial intelligence to support accessibility, differentiation of instruction and the active participation of students, as well as the importance of the responsible use of these technologies in the educational environment.

Keywords: inclusive education, artificial intelligence, Erasmus+, vocational training, digital skills, educational innovation

1. Introduction

Contemporary education is influenced by technological and social transformations that require the permanent adaptation of teaching practices. In this context, inclusive education is a priority of European education systems, aiming to ensure equal access to learning and the active participation of all students, regardless of their particularities.

Artificial intelligence is becoming a tool with significant potential in supporting school inclusion, through its ability to personalize learning experiences, facilitate access to educational resources, and support teachers in designing activities tailored to student diversity.

Participation in Erasmus+ mobility programs provides teachers with important opportunities for professional development, exchange of best practices and international collaboration. In this context, the course "Inclusive Teaching with Artificial Intelligence" was a valuable opportunity to explore the applications of artificial intelligence in education and to develop the skills necessary to use them effectively and responsibly.

2. Method

The paper is based on a qualitative reflective approach, based on direct experience of participating in the international training course held in Athens, Greece, on 18–24 May 2026. The data were collected through participatory observation, active involvement in workshops, collaborative activities, practical exercises and reflection sessions held during the six days of training. This analysis is focused on the competences developed, the pedagogical relevance of the proposed activities and the possibilities for the transfer of knowledge acquired in the teaching activity.

3. Findings

Familiarize yourself with the use of artificial intelligence in inclusive education

The first day of the course was dedicated to introducing participants to the topic of inclusive learning assisted by artificial intelligence. Teachers from different European countries had the opportunity to gain professional experience and analyse current educational challenges. Activities highlighted the role of smart technologies in supporting diversity and creating educational environments accessible to all students.

Harnessing students' strengths through AI tools

On the second day, the activities focused on identifying and developing students' strengths through an 'AI Toolkit'. Participants used applications based on artificial intelligence to make interactive presentations and to

adapt the educational content to the individual needs of the students. Practical experience has demonstrated how technology can support the differentiation of instruction and contribute to increasing students' motivation and involvement in the learning process.

Ethical aspects of the use of artificial intelligence

The third day was dedicated to the analysis of the ethical dimension of the use of artificial intelligence in education. Participants investigated the existence of biases in AI image generators and discussed their impact on the educational process. Recommendations and guidelines on the responsible use of artificial intelligence and educational data were also presented. The debates highlighted the need to develop a digital culture based on accountability, transparency and respect for ethical principles.

Designing strategies for inclusive classrooms

In the activities carried out on the fourth day, participants developed strategies for the development of inclusive classrooms, using AI tools in the educational planning process. The following activity was to identify the pedagogical motivations "Why?" and concrete implementation modalities "How?" of inclusive practices. It was also at this stage that the presentation of the participating institutions took place. The representation of the National College "Fratii Buzești" in Craiova was an opportunity to promote institutional values, academic performance and involvement in European educational projects.

AI-assisted learning in cultural and educational contexts

The activities of the fifth day took place at the Stavros Niarchos Cultural Foundation in Athens, an important cultural and educational center of Greece. The participants carried out the activity "Planning the visit with artificial intelligence", using AI tools to organize and optimize an educational route. The official visit to the National Library of Greece provided an opportunity to observe the integration of technology and cultural resources in the processes of development and information. The day ended with the final evaluation of the course and the awarding of certificates of participation.

Development of intercultural competences

The last day of the course was dedicated to the culture and heritage of Greece. Cultural activities complemented the learning experience by strengthening intercultural dialogue and developing a European perspective on education. Interaction with participants from different educational systems has contributed to broadening the professional horizon and to increasing the choice of cultural diversity as an educational resource.

4. Discussion- Conclusions

Participation in the course "Inclusive Teaching with Artificial Intelligence" has demonstrated that artificial intelligence can be a valuable tool for the development of inclusive and innovative educational practices. The activities carried out highlighted the ability of smart technologies to support the personalization of learning, the accessibility of educational resources and the adaptation of the teaching process to the individual needs of students.

An important aspect highlighted during the training was the need for responsible and ethical use of artificial intelligence. Although technology offers many opportunities, it cannot replace the role of the teacher, who remains essential in building educational relationships and supporting the socio-emotional development of students.

The international dimension of the course facilitated the exchange of best practices, professional collaboration and the development of intercultural competences. These experiences contribute to the modernization of teaching activity and to the promotion of an education oriented to the real needs of students and to the requirements of the digital society.

In conclusion, participating in this Erasmus+ mobility was a valuable professional experience, which strengthened the digital, pedagogical and intercultural skills necessary to implement modern, inclusive and student-centred educational practices.

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